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Most striking about Jeremy Lin's sudden recognition is the characterization of his personal fans and New York Knicks fans as succumbing to "Linsanity." There are two things about this portmanteau (Lin + insanity) that are striking. The first imputation is that his fans are mentally disturbed. Whether they are insane about him or being judged for their adoration is unclear. Scholars in fan studies (yes, there is such a thing!) moved away from the idea of the fan as irrational and, hence, unthinking, in the 1980s. Today, we tend to examine how fans use culture and create their own meaningful messages from that culture.

Yet, the sports media's conversation about Jeremy Lin moved---like Lin's ascent in the press---from "Who is this kid?!" to "Look at all the wacky Chinese basketball fans!" rather quickly. This focus on Chinese fans, while ignoring the fact that Lin TaiwaneseAmerican, feeds into the current media focus on China as "taking over the world" (and by "the world," most reporters really do, arrogantly, mean "America). This flattening of Asia has historically served U.S. propaganda interests and continues to do so in this time of the U.S.' imperial decline and the dominance of U.S. economists' designation of the "BRIC" (Brazil/Russia/India/China) nations. More recent sports reports, quickly exhausting the incredulous, but old news that basketball is and has been quite popular in China for decades, are now turning their focus on "reclaiming" Lin from the Chinese government's purported attempt to "appropriate" Lin as their own.¹

From the production of our gadgets to this new focus on Jeremy Lin, I'm suspicious of the U.S. sports media's focus on Lin-as-national-property narrative that merges with recent conversations and paranoia about China's industrial dominance. A good point of comparison would be the emergence of an Indian or Brazilian sports star for how sports narratives converge with public affairs programming to buttress national anxieties.

The second implication of "Linsanity" as a term is the allusion to a kind of temporary craze. Linguist Ishtla Singh notes in her book *The History of English*

(Oxford University Press, 2005): Advertising and certain types of journalistic writing (such as that in entertainment columns) provide fertile ground for blends but since many are often of the moment, they are also short-lived (hence their categorisation as nonce-formations). Take, for example, the blend Bennifer, which was used extensively in 2003 to describe the relationship between Ben Affleck and Jennifer Lopez. Bennifer, however, has since gone the way of the actual union.

Bestowing a blended label on Lin conveys that sports writers and announcers consider his ascent a fad, rather than being accountable for their own short-attention spans within a 24-hour infotainment cycle. By branding people as “Linsane,” little credit is given to fans who may have long followed Jeremy’s Lin’s basketball career with interest that isn’t embedded in racist, essentialist notions (“These people are Chinese. Lin is [not] Chinese. They must like him because he is [not] Chinese. But they seem crazy.”). Lin offers more than merely an opportunity for the U.S. media to pat itself on the back for offering Asians and Asian-Americans a role model. Across race, the nationalist tales we tell ourselves find fertile ground in imprecise assumptions about Lin’s origins: he was born in L.A. to Taiwanese parents with dual citizenship and is, therefore, not is a Chinese immigrant to the U.S. The media flounders when people and events don’t fit neatly into a bootstrap storyline. Media studies scholars and those interested in how the media generates specific political messages have a ripe opportunity here, and hopefully not a flash in the pan moment, to take a holistic look at Jeremy Lin, his fans, the media, and the sports industries’ construction of an icon and to what national purpose.

Forgive me, but I have, mercifully, run out of room to tackle the newest, inaccurate Linderived blending...wait for it...“The Year of the DragLin!”

1. “Stop the Linsanity,” *The Economist*, 20 February 2012.